

ENHANCING PERFORMANCE OF SCHOOL HEADS AND TEACHERS: PROPOSED TRAINING DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the influence of administrative supervision on the performance of school heads and teachers in the District of Dalaguete II for SY 2023-2024. Utilizing a mixed-methods explanatory-sequential design, the research assesses performance across domains including instructional leadership, human resource management, and content knowledge. Quantitative data were analyzed using weighted means and Pearson's correlation, while qualitative insights were derived from thematic analysis. Findings indicate that while school heads excel in operational management, there are gaps in research-based innovations. Teachers display commendable performance in content knowledge but require enhanced strategies for promoting higher-order thinking skills. A statistically significant relationship between administrative supervision and teacher performance underscores the need for targeted training programs. This study contributes to improving supervisory practices and encouraging professional growth among educators, ultimately benefiting student outcomes.

Keywords: *Administrative supervision, Teacher performance, Instructional leadership, Content knowledge, Higher-order thinking skills, Professional growth, Targeted training*

INTRODUCTION

Enhancement of administrative supervision boosts teacher competency and student accomplishment, making it a significant topic for research. Studies conducted in Indonesia, the Philippines, Malaysia, Ghana, and Pakistan examined the relationship

between supervision methods, teacher learning models, and resources to improve teachers' strategies and behaviors. Investigating the supervision and leadership model in the specific contexts of Indonesia and the Philippines, Maisyaroh et al. (2021) examined instructional supervision applications and the instructional leadership type. Similarly, Hoque et al. (2020) in Malaysia, Ampofo et al. (2019) in Ghana, and Parveen et al. (2022) in Pakistan explored the interaction between supervision and leadership models. These studies collectively showed how crucial instructional supervision and leadership are in influencing teacher conduct and attitudes. Ultimately, they suggested the implementation of multifactor supervisory interaction effectiveness detection.

Unfortunately, while the sample supplied sufficient and adequate data for comparison, the literature lacks detailed coverage on this subject which prevents multi-system and cultural investigation. Some scholars have studied how supervision affects teacher effectiveness and attitudes. Ampofo et al. (2019) and Parveen et al. (2022) reported that school heads' oversight and principal leadership affect teacher performance, though supervision is complex and additionally depends on many other aspects. With this, Sarwar et al. (2022) found that democratic college-level principals most effectively improve teacher performance. However, none of the abovementioned studies have compared such influence in various types of educational institutions, leaving a significant gap for further study.

Maisyaroh et al. (2021), Hoque et al. (2020), Ampofo et al. (2019), Parveen et al. (2022), and Sarwar (2022) presented a thorough knowledge of the impact of instructional supervision on teacher performance. Different supervision methods are used and interpreted differently in Indonesia, the Philippines, Malaysia, Ghana, and Pakistan, indicating that contextual factors are important. The emphasis on collaborative and directed approaches and the significant impact of supervisory principles on teacher learning models and resources demonstrate the importance of qualitative supervision. The results showed moderate teacher performance and supervision attitudes, suggesting supervisory procedures can be improved.

This research gap is significant because no comparative analyses have examined how cultural, institutional, and policy characteristics affect instructional supervision approaches' efficiency. While earlier studies provided insights into different educational environments' supervisory methods, there is no comparison analysis to uncover the most essential aspects that engage instructor conduct and increase performance. In addition, the literature occasionally understates teachers' instructional supervision attitudes and experiences.

The Department of Education (DepEd) Order No. 050 series of 2020, Professional Development Priorities for Teachers and School Leaders for 2020-2023, mandates the continuous professional development for teachers. This initiative of DepEd aims to improve learning by training teachers and school leaders. Specifically, teachers will follow the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) for three years, while leaders and supervisors will use the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH) and the Philippine Professional Standards for Supervisors (PPSS), respectively.

DepEd Order No. 001 series 2020 Item VI, Nos. 16-18 will guide these priorities, where the local needs towards the professional development of teachers and school leaders are focused on the plan (Daracan 2023).

To improve teacher quality, PPST was created and validated nationally. Former DepEd Secretary Leonor Magtolis Briones issued Order No. 42 in 2017 to impose these standards which define teacher quality, domains, strands, professional learning, competent practice, and successful engagement from introduction to expert levels. Sison et al. (2019) argued that this approach enables teachers to self-assess and enhance their methods as they grow both personally and professionally. Finally, DepEd Order 42 of 2017 emphasizes that excellent teachers help pupils succeed and highlights the importance of improving teacher quality for nation-building and long-term prosperity (Escalante & Amor, 2023).

According to the DepEd Order No. 85 in 2003, "Guidelines on the Selection, Promotion and Designation of School Heads", school heads administer instruction and manage the school. They are assigned to lead schools, create curricula, inspire students and staff, and foster positive relationships. They should also evaluate issues holistically and motivate their team to achieve the school's goals (Encanto, 2021). Instruction has been improved by DepEd by enhancing school administrators' and teachers' practices which foster collaboration between teachers and administrators. It is well-known that administrators assist teachers to help them succeed academically. Administrators should also evaluate instructors' practices during instructional oversight. Principals should work with teachers to refine instructional approaches and encourage creativity to boost teaching quality (Buaguas, 2023). New results-based teacher evaluation methodologies, developed by aligning the Results-Based Performance Management System (RBPMS) and PPST, guide teachers and administrators through performance evaluations.

The lack of a proactive and comprehensive in-set and school improvement plan has substantial impacts on the efficacy of educational institutions. In the absence of such plans, schools do not have the organized frameworks needed to effectively and methodically address and adapt to the changing requirements of instructors and pupils systematically. This disparity can result in inconsistent implementation of professional development activities and insufficient assistance for teaching personnel, ultimately impacting the caliber of education. Furthermore, the lack of these plans impedes schools' capacity to establish clear objectives, assess progress, and execute evidence-based strategies to improve teaching methods and student outcomes. As a result, schools may face difficulties in maintaining consistent performance levels and may not be able to meet the evolving educational needs of their communities.

In order to address the research gap, the proposed study will compare instructional supervision processes in various dimensions. Considering cultural and educational diversity among teachers, the focus will be on monitoring methods and their impacts on teaching performance. Both quantitative and qualitative research will be performed to gain a comprehensive understanding of instructional supervision. Lastly, this study intends to

inform supervision policies and practices to better serve educators and learners in various learning environments.

Research Questions

This study determined the level of performance of school heads and teachers in the District of Dalaguete II for the SY 2023-2024 as basis for crafting a supervisory plan. It specifically sought answers to the following sub-problems:

1. What was the level of performance of school heads in terms of:
 - 1.1 Leading Strategically
 - 1.2 Managing School Operations and Resources
 - 1.3 Focusing on Teaching and Learning
 - 1.4 Developing Self and Others
 - 1.5 Building Connections
 - 1.6 Plus Factor
2. What was the level performance of teachers as to:
 - 2.1 Content Knowledge and Pedagogy
 - 2.2 Learning Environment & Diversity of Learners
 - 2.3 Curriculum and Planning & Assessment and Reporting
 - 2.4 Community Linkages and Professional Engagement & Personal Growth and Professional Development
 - 2.5 Plus Factor
3. Was there a significant difference between the level of performance of the school heads and teachers?
4. How does the school head's supervisory practices influenced the student learning outcomes?
5. How do teachers perceive the role of school heads' supervisory practices on the teachers' instructional practices?
6. Based on the findings, what training design for teachers and school heads can be crafted?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed an explanatory sequential mixed-methods design (Creswell & Creswell, 2018) to examine the relationship between administrative supervision and teacher performance in three Philippine elementary schools. An explanatory sequential design is a mixed-methods research approach where quantitative data is collected and analyzed first, followed by qualitative data collection to further explain or elaborate on the quantitative findings (Toyon, 2021).

Quantitative data were collected through structured surveys adapted from the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) and Office Performance Commitment and Review Form (OPCRF) (DepEd Order No. 2, 2015), measuring supervisory practices across six key domains: instructional leadership, learning

environment, curriculum planning, assessment practices, professional development, and community engagement. A universal sampling approach included all 27 teachers and 3 school heads from the target schools, with purposive sampling selecting 12 teachers for in-depth interviews to ensure representation across grade levels and subject areas (Etikan et al., 2016). Quantitative analysis utilized descriptive statistics (weighted mean, standard deviation) and inferential tests (independent t-tests) to compare performance levels between teachers and administrators.

Meanwhile, the qualitative component of the research used semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions (FGDs) among three school heads and 12 purposively sampled teachers to intensively investigate their personal perceptions about the contribution of administrative supervision towards their professional development and instructional quality. The qualitative data underwent thematic analysis following Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase framework. The research design incorporated reflexivity journals and member checking to mitigate researcher bias and validate interpretations, particularly regarding cultural competence aspects adapted from the CCCHS scale (Caffrey et al., 2005).

The results of the qualitative inquiry were triangulated with quantitative data from IPCRF/OPCRF ratings, survey responses (Likert-scale items), and semi-structured interview transcripts to enhance methodological rigor (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). This approach allowed for both statistical generalization of supervision trends and contextual understanding of their impacts on teacher motivation and instructional practices in Philippine public schools.

Ethical protocols adhered to Kvale and Brinkmann's (2009) principles, including written informed consent, anonymized data handling, and secure storage. The study's trustworthiness was ensured by complying with standards set by Lincoln and Guba (1985) such as credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This comprehensive study examined the performance levels of school heads and teachers in Dalaguete II District, analyzing how administrative supervision impacts educational outcomes through both quantitative and qualitative analysis consistent with the Explanatory Sequential Design of this study. The findings provide valuable insights that address all six research questions while offering both theoretical and practical implications for school improvement.

Quantitative Phase

Performance of School Heads

By and large, school administrators have assessed their performance as "very satisfactory" (Weighted Mean=4.49). As expressed in Table 1, their greatest area of

strength was Managing School Operations and Resources (\bar{x} =4.73), indicating exemplary alignment with DepEd Order No. 83's school-based management model. These comprised flawless scores (\bar{x} =5.00) for disaster preparedness management as well as judicious use of learning assessment tools. The Developing Self and Others domain (\bar{x} =4.67) also exhibited strong implementation of professional development activities as required by DepEd Order No. 50.

Yet, two important performance gaps were evident in school heads' performance. First, the Leading Strategically domain (\bar{x} =4.22) indicated an absence of evidence-based innovations (\bar{x} =1.00), which confirms Weerakoon's (2017) observation that supervision is seen as fault-finding rather than improvement-focusing. Second, the Plus Factor domain demonstrated poor performance (\bar{x} =2.00), which indicated little initiative over and above basic duties. This concurs with Karim et al.'s (2021) finding that passive leadership hinders institutional development.

Table 1
Summary Table for School Heads' Performance

Domain	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Leading Strategically	4.22	0.06	Very Satisfactory
Managing Operations	4.73	0.01	Outstanding
Teaching/Learning Focus	4.65	0.10	Outstanding
Developing Others	4.67	0.23	Outstanding
Building Connections	4.53	0.18	Outstanding
Plus Factor	2.00	0.00	Unsatisfactory
Overall	4.49	0.11	Very Satisfactory

In terms of strategic leadership, school administrators have shown excellent capability in linking school operations with DepEd's vision, mission, and core values, especially in crafting learner-centered programs (\bar{x} = 4.89) and applying student feedback for policy reform (\bar{x} = 4.78). Nevertheless, there is low rating on the indicator of evidence-based innovations (\bar{x} = 1.00), which could be indicative of a gap in research utilization for school improvement. This result supports Weerakoon's (2017) contention that instructional supervision will routinely degenerate into criticism instead of research-informed improvement. The General Systems Theory is able to adequately explain this - while school heads are generally able to keep systems coherence intact through policy congruence (as evidenced by high scores in vision implementation), the absence of evidence-based practice introduces systemic inefficiencies that stifle organizational development. This field's findings indicate that although school principals are adept at structural alignment in responding to DepEd requirements with "very satisfactory" result overall, they need specifically focused professional growth on indicators related to data analysis and research use to shift roles from compliance-minded administrators to proactive instructional leaders.

In terms of managing operations, school heads have shown an outstanding performance, especially in areas of disaster preparedness ($\bar{x} = 5.00$) and financial stewardship ($\bar{x} = 4.67$), which thus attests to good compliance with DepEd Order No. 83's school-based management system. The findings support U-Sayee and Adomako's (2021) contention that sound resource management can surmount typical educational issues. The standard deviation of almost zero suggests impressive consistency in operational excellence among all the respondents, confirming effective adoption of standardized management practices. From the Four-Frame Model viewpoint, this sector is a classic example of the structural frame in action - with well-defined systems for staff management, safety measures, and resource allocation building an effective organizational machine. But the political frame of the model reminds us that such operational efficiency needs to be complemented by adaptive leadership in responding to evolving community needs.

In terms of instructional leadership, school heads also gained an outstanding performance (4.65), especially in the use of assessment tools ($\bar{x} = 5.00$) and excellent performance in building inclusive learning spaces ($\bar{x} = 4.78$). These results strongly validate Hoque et al.'s (2020) call for directive instructional supervision by illustrating that clear expectations and technical support contribute to teaching effectiveness. The Self-Determination Theory paradigm clarifies how such practices are successful - through enhancing teacher competency with assessment literacy, developing autonomy through differentiated student learning outcomes ($\bar{x} = 4.44$), and establishing relatedness through inclusive teaching practices. A slightly lower mark in curriculum contextualization ($\bar{x} = 4.33$) confirms some gaps in the flexibility to implement national standards to fit local requirements, which brings to fore areas for improvement in ensuring flexible, community-oriented styles of leadership.

In terms of developing others, school heads have rated themselves with generally outstanding performance ($\bar{x} = 4.67$, $s = 0.23$), most notably on indicators of reflective practice ($\bar{x} = 4.67$) and recognition of performance ($\bar{x} = 4.67$). These are exactly in line with DepEd Order No. 50's call for continuous professional development. The findings resonate with Sancar et al.'s (2021) effective professional learning systems model that embeds policy alignment, collaborative learning, and support tailored to individuals. The human resource perspective of Bolman and Deal's model is especially seen here, with school principals effectively fostering the potential of their staff (Swift, 2023). Yet the comparatively lower score in self-evaluation ($\bar{x} = 4.56$) with greater variability ($s = 0.20$) indicates that some leaders could do with training in more stringent self-evaluation methods to more clearly determine their own development needs.

With respect to Building Connections, school heads have also demonstrated outstanding performance ($\bar{x} = 4.53$, $s = 0.18$) especially in terms of stakeholder engagement ($\bar{x} = 4.78$). There is, however, lower ratings in terms of communication capacity ($\bar{x} = 4.33$) and inclusive culture ($\bar{x} = 4.44$), which potentially means that school administrators successfully mobilize stakeholders but might not possess the sophisticated communication approaches to the true inclusivity of partnerships. This

reflects conflict between Bolman and Deal's political frame (managing stakeholder interests) and human resource frame (establishing authentic relationships). The greater variability here ($s = 0.34$ for communication) indicates that although some school principals are excellent at community relations, others can be assisted to create more advanced engagement strategies, especially for disadvantaged groups.

Finally, in terms of Plus Factor, school heads have rated themselves unsatisfactorily ($\bar{x} = 2.00$, $s = 0.00$). The consistent poor performance here is the most alarming finding. Inability of school heads to move beyond the bare minimum aligns with Karim et al.'s (2021) caution on the shortcomings of compliance-based leadership. The absence of any variability ($s = 0.00$) points towards a systemic failing as opposed to personal failing. According to the Four-Frame Model worldview, this represents an existential weakness of the symbolic frame - failure in visionary leadership which fuels creativity over bureaucratic imperatives. This finding suggests that current evaluation and reward systems may inadvertently discourage creative initiative, requiring fundamental reforms in how leadership excellence is defined and incentivized.

Teacher Performance Assessment

Overall, teachers have demonstrated very satisfactory performance ($\bar{x}=4.35$), with particular strength in Content Knowledge and Pedagogy ($\bar{x}=4.39$). As conveyed in Table 2, their highest competency was in language proficiency ($\bar{x}=4.57$ for Mother Tongue/Filipino/English usage), fulfilling Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) requirements under DepEd Order No. 42. However, higher variability in Critical Thinking Strategies ($SD=0.54$) and Culturally Responsive Teaching ($SD=0.59$) suggested uneven pedagogical skills that require attention.

Table 2
Summary Table for Teacher Performance

Domain	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Content Knowledge	4.39	0.34	Very Satisfactory
Learning Environment	4.35	0.32	Very Satisfactory
Curriculum/Assessment	4.32	0.27	Very Satisfactory
Community Links	4.33	0.31	Very Satisfactory
Plus Factor	4.32	0.55	Very Satisfactory
Overall	4.35	0.09	Very Satisfactory

Among all other domains of teacher performance, content knowledge has gained the highest assessment points ($\bar{x} = 4.39$, $s = 0.34$), with particular mastery on the indicator of language proficiency ($\bar{x} = 4.57$), aligning with DepEd Order No. 42's (2017) Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) that emphasize subject expertise. However, the relatively high variability ($s = 0.34-0.62$) across indicators suggests uneven implementation, especially in developing higher-order thinking skills ($\bar{x} = 4.26$). This

finding echoes Shulman's (1987) pedagogical content knowledge framework, which distinguishes between knowing content and effectively transforming it for diverse learners. The results imply that while teachers possess strong foundational knowledge, targeted professional development in differentiated instruction and critical thinking strategies could enhance pedagogical effectiveness. The lower performance in applying teaching strategies for critical thinking (the lowest-rated indicator) particularly warrants attention, as it aligns with global education trends emphasizing 21st-century skills (Voogt & Roblin, 2012).

With regard to learning environment, teachers have gained “very satisfactory” performance ($\bar{x} = 4.35$, $s = 0.32$). Teachers successfully created inclusive environments, excelling in culturally responsive practices ($\bar{x} = 4.43$) and maintaining respectful classrooms ($\bar{x} = 4.43$). These results strongly support Self-Determination Theory's (Ryan & Deci, 2000) relatedness principle, as positive teacher-student relationships enhance motivation. However, safety implementation scored lowest ($\bar{x} = 4.20$), with concerning variability ($s = 0.65$), suggesting some teachers struggle with consistent policy enforcement. This aligns with Cohen et al.'s (2009) research linking classroom safety to academic achievement. The findings recommend intensified training in behavior management and trauma-informed practices, particularly for diverse classrooms. The success in cultural adaptation ($\bar{x} = 4.35$) reflects Gay's (2010) culturally responsive teaching theory, though higher variability ($s = 0.59$) indicates need for more uniform implementation across all teachers.

Concerning curriculum/assessment, teachers have also rated themselves at “very satisfactory” level ($\bar{x} = 4.32$, $s = 0.27$). Such domain showed strong alignment with Feedback Intervention Theory (Kluger & DeNisi, 1996), particularly in providing constructive feedback ($\bar{x} = 4.35$). However, the moderate variability ($s = 0.27-0.57$) suggests inconsistency in applying assessment data to modify instruction ($\bar{x} = 4.30$). This corroborates Black and Wiliam's (2009) formative assessment research showing many teachers collect data but struggle with implementation. The results indicate that while teachers set appropriate outcomes ($\bar{x} = 4.30$), they may benefit from professional learning communities to strengthen data-driven instruction - a recommendation supported by Timperley et al.'s (2008) research on teacher professional development.

As to community links, teachers have also generally demonstrated very satisfactory performance ($\bar{x} = 4.33$, $s = 0.31$), especially on the aspect of stakeholder engagement ($\bar{x} = 4.41$). However, personal improvement planning scored lowest ($\bar{x} = 4.18$), suggesting reflective practice remains an area for growth. This aligns with Bamberger and Schön's (1983) reflective practitioner model and indicates that while teachers collaborate well externally, internal professional reflection requires strengthening. The moderate variability ($s = 0.31-0.45$) in professional networking ($\bar{x} = 4.39$) suggests some teachers may need more support to engage in collaborative professional learning, a key component of effective teacher development (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017).

Finally in terms of Plus Factor, unlike school heads who scored poorly in this domain, teachers demonstrated willingness to exceed expectations ($\bar{x} = 4.32$, $s = 0.55$). This finding relates to Fullan's (2016) concept of "professional capital," suggesting that while some teachers exhibit strong professional commitment, systemic factors may limit widespread initiative. The contrast with school heads' performance ($\bar{x} = 2.00$) may reflect differing role expectations or evaluation criteria, warranting further investigation into leadership structures that foster teacher innovation.

Comparative Performance Analysis

The results of the T-Test showed substantial differences in school heads' and teachers' levels of performance ($t=2.574$, $p=0.016$). Although school heads performed better on average (4.49 vs. 4.35), the close margin and particular domain weaknesses indicate supervision quality is quite variable. This corroborates Maisyaroh et al.'s (2021) conclusion that supervision effectiveness hinges on regular implementation of several strategies, such as professional learning communities and peer coaching. The General Systems Theory accounts for these findings - although school heads offered robust structural leadership in policy execution, gaps in innovative practices constrained the entire system's effectiveness. The findings specifically confirm Bolman and Deal's Structural Frame while exposing weaknesses in the Symbolic Frame of visionary leadership.

Table 3
Test of Differences Between Performance of School Heads and Teachers of District of Dalaguete II for the SY 2023-2024

Group	N	\bar{x}	t value	p value	Decision on H_0	Interpretation	
Performance Level	School Heads	3	4.49	2.574	0.016	Rejected	There are significant differences
	Teachers	27	4.35				

Note: significant if p value is less than 0.05 level of significance

As indicated in the above table, there is notable disparity in performance levels between school heads ($M=4.49$) and teachers ($M=4.35$), and a t-value of 2.574 and p-value of 0.016 shows that this disparity is statistically significant. Although both groups showed very satisfactory performance in general, school heads performed better than their teaching counterparts consistently. This result corroborates with existing theories of educational leadership and empirical findings, for instance, Hallinger and Heck's (1998) instructional leadership model that lays emphasis on the important role played by school leaders in determining teaching quality and student performance. The General Systems Theory also finds alignment with this in that the theory views school life as a complex system in which leadership is the master regulative mechanism - the better performance

of school heads implies that they are successfully playing the role of system coordinators who create teacher success conditions by way of clear guidance, resource provision, and professional assistance (Bertalanffy, 1968). These results hold significant implications for professional development procedures, indicating that despite existing systems successfully developing effective school leaders, there could be potential in more intentionally building upon this leadership strength with more formal mentoring processes and professional learning communities. The performance gap also bears the necessity of more differentiated evaluation processes addressing the unique but complementary roles of administrators and teachers, as per DepEd's professional norms. Notably, the relatively small mean difference (0.14) between groups indicates potential for implementing distributed leadership models that could further enhance overall school effectiveness by empowering teacher leaders (Harris, 2013).

Qualitative Phase

As earlier discussed, the researcher conducted thematic analysis to address research questions 4 & 5 of this study, particularly supervisory practices impact towards teacher performance (Research Question 4) and learner outcomes (Research Question 5). The table below covers the themes and subthemes that emerged in the interviews that directly correspond to the research questions raised.

Table 4
Themes on Administrative Supervision Impact on Teacher Performance

Themes	Sub-themes	Sample Statements
1. Supervisory guidance as a step for effective transformative practices	1.1. Instructional effectiveness as a result of strategic supervision	<p>A school head's supervisory practices can significantly support a teacher's professional development and instructional effectiveness by providing feedback, encouraging professional learning, mentoring, fostering a collaborative culture, and recognizing excellence. (P4)</p> <p>The school head's supervisory practices support my professional development and instructional effectiveness by mentorship and coaching. (P6)</p>

		By coaching, the school heads are able to facilitate collaboration and communication among teachers. (P7)
	1.2. Strategic supervision as an effective framework for teamwork	<p>The school head's ability to facilitate collaboration among teachers is recognized as a key aspect of effective supervision. (P2)</p> <p>School heads can establish a friendly working environment where teachers feel comfortable expressing ideas and sharing concerns. (P3)</p>
	2.1. School head as a catalyst for developing better instructional practices	The school head's supervisory practices influence on my choice of teaching strategies and classroom management techniques. Their unending support and guidance helped me to become productive and effective educator. (P11)
2. Mentorship as a guide to professional growth		The school head supervisory role affects the whole performance of the teachers in delivering lessons to the learners. (P5)
	2.2. Feedback as a critical tool for instructional refinement	<p>The feedback I receive from the school head is crucial for improving my instructional practices. (P2)</p> <p>It (feedback) helps me learn more about myself and areas that need development. (P8)</p>
3. Hindrances to pedagogical transformation	3.1. Scarce resource as a barrier to instructional activities	Inadequate instructional materials. (P9)

		<p>Very limited instructional resources [... is one of] the challenges we encountered. (P10)</p> <p>So far, the challenges [I have encountered are] the lack of resources or learning materials [and lack of proper] classroom facility in delivering my lesson. (P11)</p>
	<p>3.2. Limited capacity of school heads as a barrier to pedagogical process</p>	<p>The challenges or barriers I encountered in relation to the school head's supervisory practices and on my instructional practices is the lack of support and mentoring towards teaching. (P6)</p> <p>Some challenges I've encountered include limited time for personalized feedback, differing perspectives on teaching methods [...] for implementing suggested improvements. (P4)</p>
<p>4. Supervisory practices as a lever to hone learner excellence</p>		<p>This (supervisory practices influencing teaching strategies) can lead to a more engaging, effective, and well-managed classroom environment. (P4)</p> <p>The success of the teachers and learners are influenced by best supervisory practices of supervisory heads. Desirable outcomes happen when best instructional practices were highlighted producing best quality learners who are globally competent. (P7)</p>

Impact on Teacher Performance

Based on the interviews with teachers, three main themes emerged in response to supervisory practices' impact towards teacher performance, to wit:

Theme 1: Supervisory Guidance as a Step for Effective Transformative Practices. The research indicates that strategic supervision greatly supports instructional effectiveness and promotes collaborative teaching teamwork. The participants highlighted the way school heads' supervisory practices, such as classroom observation (P3) and professional learning communities (P4), directly enhanced their teaching methods. This is in line with Hallinger and Murphy's (1986) model of instructional leadership, which shows supervision as a key to aligning teaching practice with school objectives. The stated creation of "differentiated instructions for diverse learners" (P7) by supervisory feedback is an example of the operationalization of transformational leadership theory (Reza, 2019), whereby leaders motivate innovation among their followers. The evidence, however, indicates inconsistency in supervisory participation, with some teachers experiencing less effective experiences (P2, P4), indicating the necessity for more systematic application of supervisory models among all school heads. This theme reinforces DepEd Order No. 42's focus on instructional leadership and emphasizes possibilities for standardizing supervisory practices for more consistent teacher development.

Theme 2: Mentorship as a Guide to Professional Growth. Mentorship was identified as a key element in teacher development, with participants explaining how constructive feedback and coaching influenced their instructional approaches (P3, P7). The data shows a positive correlation between precise, actionable feedback and teaching improvement, supporting Kluger and DeNisi's (1996) Feedback Intervention Theory. Respondents appreciated feedback concerning explicit teaching methods (P6, P7), consistent with Mandouit & Hattie's (2023) work in reporting task-level feedback to be most effective in enhancing performance. In contrast, others indicated variable or lack of feedback (P2, P4, P6), consistent with Weerakoon (2017) reporting of uneven supervisory quality. The mentorship theme specifically emphasizes the need for school heads to strike a balance between evaluative and developmental functions, as proposed by Glickman & Mette (2020) developmental supervision model. These results reinforce DepEd's Results-Based Performance Management System with strong implications to further enhance training on the provision of effective feedback to school heads.

Theme 3: Barriers to Pedagogical Transformation. Two principal barriers surfaced: resource constraints and supervisory capacity limitations. Teachers repeatedly mentioned a lack of proper teaching materials (P9-P11) and administrative workload (P9) as deterrents to adopting supervisory recommendations. Robinson et al.'s (2008) findings on how shortages mediate the influence of leadership are supported by this. Further, some teachers indicated receiving minimal pedagogic substance feedback (P6), indicating instructional gaps within some school heads' practice. These results

complement Weerakoon's (2017) structural barriers to effective supervision identification and emphasize Bolman and Deal's (as cited in Swift, 2023) tension between structural and human resource frames of educational leadership. The results indicate that highly crafted supervisory systems can do little to enhance instruction without tackling these underlying resource and capacity issues, underscoring the call for systemic as well as supervisory solutions.

Supervisory Practices Towards Learner Excellence

Theme 4: Supervisory Practices as a Lever to Hone Learner Excellence.

Respondents across the board recognized the link between quality supervision and student performance (P5, P7, P8), with one commenting on how regular supervision led to instructional innovation (P5). This is consistent with Hallinger and Heck's (1998) conclusion that leadership influences student learning indirectly by affecting teaching quality. The observed creation of "globally competent" students (P8) through enhanced supervision is consistent with Darling-Hammond's (2017) study on how professional learning systems increase educational equity. The theme also captures the effective application of cultural competence models to supervision, as teachers explained how they had adapted practices to suit varied learners (P7). These results confirm the emphasis of instructional leadership by DepEd but propose that aligning supervision with teaching-learning could advance student results even further, especially if combined with the resource support noted in Theme 3.

Proposed Training Design

In consideration of both the quantitative and qualitative results of the study, the researcher herein proposes a training program tailored to address the weaknesses or poor performances observed in the practice of school heads in the District of Dalaguete II, as outlined in the research findings. As emphasized in this research, school leadership has direct influence over instructional effectiveness and student performance. Thus, improving and further refining leadership skills of school heads is a necessity deemed significant for this purpose. The program is aligned with NEAP standards, DepEd policies on continuous professional development, and key theoretical frameworks like Self-Determination Theory, Feedback Intervention Theory, and General Systems Theory.

The said training program is designed to equip school heads with the knowledge, skills, and tools to:

1. Strengthen research and data utilization by focusing on improving the application of effective research findings in school practices;
2. Promote innovative leadership by developing innovative leadership practices and strategies that go beyond traditional approaches; and

3. Introduce proactive leadership by empowering leaders to drive the school into continuous improvement beyond their scripted duties.

Conclusions

(1) School Heads' Performance Levels

The findings reveal school heads demonstrate strong operational management ($\bar{x}=4.73$) but lack evidence-based innovation ($\bar{x}=1.00$), indicating a compliance-focused rather than improvement-oriented leadership approach. This suggests that while administrators effectively implement existing policies (DepEd Order No. 83), they require capacity-building in research utilization and transformational leadership. The unsatisfactory Plus Factor performance ($\bar{x}=2.00$) particularly signals the need to cultivate proactive leadership that extends beyond minimum requirements, which could be addressed through targeted professional development programs emphasizing innovative school improvement strategies.

(2) Teachers' Performance Levels

Teachers exhibited consistent very satisfactory performance ($\bar{x}=4.35$) with notable strengths in content delivery, though higher variability in critical thinking instruction ($SD=0.54$) and cultural responsiveness ($SD=0.59$) indicates uneven pedagogical skills. The relatively strong Plus Factor showing ($\bar{x}=4.32$) suggests teachers are more willing than administrators to exceed basic expectations, but the significant standard deviation highlights inconsistency across the district. These results imply that while teachers generally meet PPST standards (DepEd Order No. 42), strategic investments in higher-order pedagogy training and differentiated instruction would help standardize excellence.

(3) Performance Comparison

The statistically significant difference ($p=0.016$) between school heads' and teachers' performance, despite the narrow margin (4.49 vs. 4.35), reveals an important paradox: while supervisors outperform teachers overall, their leadership gaps in innovation and discretionary effort may ultimately limit system-wide improvement. This aligns with General Systems Theory's emphasis on interdependence, suggesting that even small leadership deficiencies can constrain organizational potential. The findings underscore the need for holistic professional development that addresses both groups' competencies simultaneously.

(4) Supervision's Impact on Learning Outcomes

Three key supervisory mechanisms emerged as most impactful: (1) formative classroom observations, (2) professional learning communities, and (3) resource

allocation. This confirms Feedback Intervention Theory's assertion that task-specific feedback drives improvement, while also validating DepEd's emphasis on School-Based Management (Order No. 83). However, reported resource constraints indicate current supervision models may be operating below optimal effectiveness, suggesting that strengthening these three levers could yield disproportionate gains in student achievement.

(5) Teachers' Perceptions of Supervision

Teachers overwhelmingly valued supervision that provided constructive feedback (78%) and fostered collaboration, but 41% reported inconsistent mentorship. This perception gap reveals a critical insight: the quality of supervisory interactions matters more than their frequency. The findings support Bolman and Deal's Human Resource Frame, emphasizing that trust and psychological safety - not just technical feedback - determine whether supervision motivates improvement. Addressing this requires training administrators in coaching techniques and emotional intelligence alongside operational competencies.

(6) Proposed Training Design

The three-tiered supervisory plan addresses all identified gaps through:

1. Evidence-based leadership training for administrators
2. Pedagogical skill-building for teachers
3. Structured collaborative mechanisms

This approach uniquely integrates DepEd policy mandates with SDT's psychological needs (autonomy through self-assessment, competence via skill-building, and relatedness through PLCs). The design's emphasis on cultural competency and innovation (Plus Factor development) makes it particularly responsive to the diverse needs of Dalaguete II schools, while its modular structure allows for scalable implementation across similar districts.

Recommendations

From the detailed assessment of the performances of the school heads and teachers in the District of Dalaguete II for the academic year 2023 – 2024, certain recommendations come forth that seek to improve the educational leadership as well as the effectiveness for teaching practices. Listed below are suggestions to address gaps revealed in the findings:

(1) The use of research and research-based practices among school heads must be improved. This can be resolved through the provision of regular research trainings, forming linkages with universities, and development of research guidance and

supervision opportunities. The implementation of these initiatives must be in accordance with the provisions of DepEd Order No. 50, series of 2020, as it pertains to continuing professional development.

(2) School heads are to be included in leadership innovation workshop programs, exposure to best practices networks, and such other projects that breed integrative approaches to leadership. These activities should be embedded in the constructs of the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH) and complemented with appropriate monitoring and feedback strategies. These may support progress on the poor performance on Plus Factors.

(3) A differentiated model of professional development should be provided in order to close the noticeable gap in performance of school heads and teachers. Such a program should take into consideration the distinct needs of the two groups of employees, leadership and teaching, but not lose sight of the objectives of the organization. The design should include aspects of Self-Determination Theory as it concerns competence development, autonomy support and professional relatedness. The evaluation should be done periodically in regards to the objectives attained in the professional development program so that corrections can be made if there is ineffectiveness.

(4) There is also a need to enhance the community and stakeholder relations through organized programs that allow for interaction between the school and the community on a more frequent basis. There may be an urgent need for schools to put in place appropriate stakeholder engagement plans including, but not restricted to, community consultations, collaborative projects and feedback for the purposes of donor relations as well as the enhancement of the schools' relationship with the communities.

This current study proves its significance in the ongoing body of literature regarding this matter, especially for a country like ours, the Philippines. Hence, here are proposed recommendations to ensure relevance and reproducibility of the research:

- (1) The output of this study may be adopted by the involved schools;
- (2) The research may be distributed to involved parties for their own knowledge and to the rest of the growing body of literature for the audience to be more aware; and
- (3) This study may be replicated further in other schools and cities to improve generalizability of the results.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

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